

NFDI4Earth x DMP4NFDI Basic Service

Online Workshop

Ivonne Anders, Katja Diederichs, Hannes Fuchs, Klaus Getzlaff, Marisabel Gonzalez-Ocanto, Christin Henzen, Christiane Schmidt, Sabine Schönau, Stefan Thiemann, David Wallace, Jürgen Windeck

December 2024

A decorative graphic at the bottom of the slide features a dark blue curved shape at the base. Above it, a light blue background contains two white circles of different sizes. These circles are connected to each other and to the base by several white curved lines, creating a network-like or orbital pattern.

Agenda

- 11:00-11:10 **Welcome** (*Christin Henzen*)
- 11:10-11:30 **DMP4NFDI Basic Service** (*Jürgen Windeck and Sabine Schönau*)
- 11:30-11:40 **Use Case Helmholtz Data Hub E&E** (*Hannes Fuchs and Sabine Schönau*)
- 11:40-11:50 **Use Case DMP at Deutschen Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ)** (*Ivonne Anders*)
- 11:50-12:00 **Use Case DMP at Universität Hamburg** (*Stefan Thiemann*)
- 12:00-12:50 **Extended Q&A Session**
- 12:50-13:00 **Summary and next steps** (*all*)

Welcome and setting the scene

Christin Henzen, TU Dresden

December 2024

Setting the scene

- Data Management Plans (DMPs) support all phases of the research data life cycle
- Earth System Sciences community is diverse -> different needs to manage DMPs & templates
- NFDI4Earth has no „dedicated“ DMP Measure
- Our central support services: User Support Network & OneStop4All
- In NFDI4Earth, institutional efforts driven by our partners
- NFDI DMP4NFDI Basic Service addresses cross-consortial needs

User Perspective

Our aims for this workshop

- Bring together DMP service providers and users as well as interested colleagues in general and with the DMP4NFDI team
- Learn more about community needs towards DMP in ESS as impulses for
 - Stimulating interactions in the related **NFDI section working groups**
 - Initiating follow-up discussions with **DMP4NFDI and active use case partners**
 - Preparing **NFDI basic service decision process** with NFDI4Earth steering group
 - DMP4NFDI is an NFDI Basic Services
 - NFDI Basic Services need approval of consortia (1st phase: 25%, 2nd phase: 50%, ...)
 - See: <https://base4nfdi.de/process/criteria-for-basic-services>,
<https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2coordinate/steering-group>

DMP4NFDI

a Basic Service for Data Management Planning

Date: 2024-12-13

From document to machine-actionability

Vision for DMPs

Die Nachnutzung von Software anderer Urheber*innen wird im Sinne der guten wissenschaftlichen Praxis gemäß der Software Citation Principles¹² zitiert.

3 Dokumentation und Datenqualität

Die anonymisierten Forschungsdaten der Bedarfserhebung und die Skripte der Software R werden auf dem fachübergreifenden Repositorium Zenodo¹³ veröffentlicht. Von einer Veröffentlichung der Ergebnisse von RISE-DE wurde abgesehen (vgl. Abschnitt 6).

Im Sinne der FAIR-Prinzipien¹⁴ werden die Daten in Zenodo durch Metadaten beschrieben, die sich am DataCite-Metadaten-Schema¹⁵ orientieren (u.a. Abstract, freie Schlagwörter und DCC-Klassifikation). Darüber hinaus wird den Daten eine Dokumentation in Form einer README-Datei hinzugefügt, welche die durchgeführten Arbeitsschritte zur bestmöglichen Nachnutz- und Reproduzierbarkeit umfasst, und ein Codebook, das die Variablen und ihre Werte, die als Spaltenbezeichnungen im Datensatz genutzt wurden, erklärt.

Dem Datensatz wird durch das Repositorium Zenodo ein persistenter Identifier (DOI) automatisch hinzugefügt, der den Datensatz eindeutig referenzierbar macht und die Wiederauffindbarkeit gewährleistet. Zenodo ermöglicht zudem die Weitergabe der Metadaten an das frei verfügbare europäische Forschungsinformationssystem OpenAire¹⁶ und an die DOI-Vergabeagentur CrossRef¹⁷.

Die Projektdaten werden getrennt nach Typ und Format in verschiedenen Verzeichnissen gespeichert (z. B. CSV-Dateien in einem „data/tabular“-Verzeichnis, alle R-Skripte gesammelt in einem „src“- oder „scripts“-Verzeichnis).

¹²Smith, Arfon M., Daniel S. Katz, Kyle E. Niemeyer, und FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group. 2016. Software citation principles. PeerJ Computer Science 2: e86. doi:10.7717/peerj-cs.86.

¹³Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/> (zugegriffen: 31.10.2022).

¹⁴Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, u. a. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific Data, 3 (1), 160018. doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18).

¹⁵DataCite Metadaten-Schema. <https://schema.datacite.org/> (zugegriffen: 18.10.2022).

¹⁶vgl. OpenAire Explore. <https://explore.openaire.eu/> (zugegriffen: 31.10.2022).

¹⁷vgl. die „Zenodo principles“. <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/> (zugegriffen: 31.10.2022).

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¹⁷vgl. die „Zenodo principles“. <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/> (zugegriffen: 31.10.2022).

A Vision for Data Management Plans in the NFDI

infra-dmp

- Shortcomings of current DMP practices
 - focussing on the text
 - services are not connected to the DMP
 - no up-to-date information
 - Time-consuming to fill in
- machine-actionable DMPs* in the NFDI
 - structured data
 - connecting services
 - connecting researchers, service providers & other stakeholders during the research process

* e.g. Bakos, A., Miksa, T., Rauber, A. (2018), https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-00066-0_6

A Vision for Data Management Plans in the NFDI

What DMPs (-templates, -tools) can do

- Communicate standard workflows and best practices via DMP templates and tools (BLV goals for NFDI*)
- Raise awareness for data management issues
- Support quality assurance
- Connect all involved stakeholders
- Support the creation of FAIR data products

A Vision for Data Management Plans in the
NFDI

Authors

Katja Diederichs, Celia Krause, Marina Lemaire, Marco Reidelbach,
Jürgen Windeck

Version 1.0

January 2024

* Bund-Länder-Vereinbarung zu Aufbau und Förderung einer Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) vom 26. November 2018. BAnz AT 21.12.2018 B10.
<https://www.gwk-bonn.de/fileadmin/Redaktion/Dokumente/Papers/NFDI.pdf>

DMP4NFDI

Service and technical concept

Central objective: *establish and foster the NFDI-wide use and application of maDMPs and maSMPs**

- hosting of open-source tool RDMO for the consortia
- coordination and support of template creation and their standardisation
- guidance, training and support for DMP-responsible staff in consortia

* and analogues

DMP4NFDI

Service

customisable
RDMO clients for
each consortium

Separate test and
production
environments

Integration with
service portfolio

Support for
template
development

One database for
shared use of
templates

Centralised
vocabulary to
ensure
interoperability

DMP template
framework

Training for
consortia staff

DMP4NFDI

NFDI DMP Template Framework

Common and standardised framework to support template creation and customisation via modules

Compatible to international maDMP standard

Miksa, T., Walk, P., & Neish, P. (2020). <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00039>

DMP4NFDI

Service integrations

- Dynamically generated option sets
 - display repositories from re3data.org
 - search through instrument database
 - terminology services
- Integrations with project management tools, e.g. OpenProject
- Export to knowledge graphs (MaRDMO)
- DMP publication via Zenodo
- ...

The image displays two screenshots of a web application interface for instrument selection. The top screenshot shows a search for 'losgatos' with a list of results, where 'LosGatos AWI 3K43000001142' is highlighted. The bottom screenshot shows the same interface with the selected instrument's details filled in: Type Name 'spectrometer', Name 'losgatos_awi_1142', and Serial '3K43000001142'.

Windeck, J., Schröder, M., Frenzel, J., Kusmierz, S., Fuchs, H., & Klar, J. (2024). <https://doi.org/10.17192/bfdm.2024.2.8629>

DMP4NFDI

Use cases

- productive
 - NFDI4Ing
 - NFDI4Chem
- test
 - NFDI4Culture
 - NFDI4Memory
 - NFDI4Earth
 - MaRDI
 - FAIRagro
- collecting requirements
 - NFDI4Biodiversity

What are the plans for the Initialisation phase and outlook?

- Software requirements analysis (use cases, RDMO feedback feature)
- RDMO hosting for use cases
- Prototypes and concepts for service integration
- Develop DMP template framework
- RDMO support
- specialized RDMO training

- Incubator projects
- successive standardisation of DMP templates/modules
- RDMO maintenance/update workflows
- additional RDMO features as required
- refinement of operating model

- *Sustainability*
- *Interoperability*

DMP4NFDI

Integration phase

- Incubator projects (3-6 months)
 - Hosting RDMO
 - Template development
 - Integration of RDMO with other services
 - Support & training
 - Outreach to community
- Submission planned Jan 22nd

DMP4NFDI

Team

RDMO Hosting & Service integration

David Wallace
Jürgen Windeck

Template Standardisation

Sabine Schönau

Support and Training

Katja Diederichs
Marisabel Gonzalez-Ocanto

Thank You !

Use Case Helmholtz Data Hub E&E (Hannes Fuchs und Sabine Schönauf)

MOSES-DMP

MOSES DMP

04/2024

Presentation of the MOSES catalog idea

Realization in RDMO possible?

General presentation on the work in RDMO

- Catalog development
- Hierarchy
- Attributes

Question	Data Management Plan Guidance	Type of Input Field	Label	REACT
1.1 Name of the Campaign:	Please provide a descriptive name for this campaign. This information will be displayed in the MOSES metadata Portal.	Freitextfeld	MOSES-Portal	
1.2 Project keyword:	Please select the corresponding MOSES Event Chain for this campaign	Multi-Choice mit: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Neutronen • Astrobiological Extremes • Ocean Drilling • Permafrost Thaw 	MOSES-Portal	
1.3 Summary / Description of the Campaign:	Please provide a descriptive summary of the campaign.	Freitextfeld	MOSES-Portal	
1.4 Start Date:	Please provide the start date of the campaign / data collection activity.	Datumsfelder	MOSES-Portal	
1.5 End Date:	Please provide the end date of the campaign / data collection activity.	Datumsfelder	MOSES-Portal	
1.6 Location:	Please provide bounding box coordinates of the research area (latitude in decimal degrees). North must be greater than South.	Vier zusammengehörende Eingabefelder vorangeht des korrekten Formats: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • North [-90.0 to 90.0] • East [-180.0 to 180.0] • South [-90.0 to 90.0] • West [-180.0 to 180.0] 	MOSES-Portal	
1.7 Name of the project lead / chief / principal investigator(s) or main researcher(s):	Please provide full contact information: name, institution, address, email, phone. Note: this person(s) is/are responsible for creating and maintaining this document until the end of the data life cycle.	5 Eingabefelder für jeden Eintrag (1 Eintrag besteht aus: Vor- und Zuname, Forschungsstruktur/Institution, Adresse, Email, Telefon, Beruf)		
1.8 Name of person responsible for managing data for the entire campaign:	Please provide a name as a contact for data management for this campaign. Note: that this needs to be someone who has overall responsibility for data acquisition, processing, quality control, documentation, and preservation. This could be the PI or a designee.	5 Eingabefelder für jeden Eintrag (1 Eintrag besteht aus: Vor- und Zuname, Forschungsstruktur/Institution, Adresse, Email, Telefon)		
1.9 Collaborating Agencies / Organizations / Institutes:	Please name the collaborating institutes of this campaign	Checkboxen mit: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alfred Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung • Forschungszentrum Jülich 		

MOSES DMP

05/2024 – 08/2024

- Presentation of further editing via video recording
- First version of the catalog created and edited
- Catalog-specific questions
 - Classification in questions to be solved technically (e.g. plugins) and existing RDMO solutions
- RDMO-User-specific questions
- Further questions/problems answered
- Personal feedback on the catalog
- ...

MOSES DMP

09/2024 – 12/2024

- Presentation of the MOSES catalog in different contexts
 - e.g. DMP4NFDI-Workshop 09/2024
- Feedback from test users of the catalog incorporated
- Import of the catalog into the NFDI4Earth test client

<https://rdmo-test.nfdi4earth.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de>

MOSES DMP

upcoming

- RDMO Core Team MOSES completes the development + testing of the MOSES catalog on the test client
- MOSES coordination invites MOSES data manager team --> Presentation of the prototype
- MOSES data managers apply the catalog to various test campaigns and provide feedback
- MOSES coordination informs DataHub about the current status of the prototype and the next planned steps (including the connection / visibility of the MOSES RDMO DMPs in the Earth Data Portal)

Core Team:

Claudia Schütze (UFZ),
Corinna Rebmann
(KIT),
Carsten Schirnick
(GEOMAR),
Matthias Riße (FZJ),
Hannes Fuchs (GFZ),
Beate Hetenyi (GFZ),
Ute Weber (UFZ)

RDMO Sensor Search Plugin

- Information exists already in other Systems
- Usage of RDMO Plugins for information exchange
- Automatic fill out relevant questions

DEMO

Demo time...

Additional Links

- Test-Mandant: <https://rdmo-test.nfdi4earth.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/projects/>
- MOSES:
 - <https://www.ufz.de/moses/>
 - <https://www.gfz-potsdam.de/sektion/fernerkundung-und-geoinformatik/projekte/moses>
- Earth Data Portal des Data Hub Erde und Umwelt: <https://earth-data.de/>

Demo: RDMO Sensor Search Plugin

Hannes Fuchs

RDMO Sensor Search Plugin

- Information exists already in other Systems
- Usage of RDMO Plugins for information exchange
- Automatic fill out relevant questions

Demo: Search for Instrument in registries

The screenshot shows the RDMO Sandbox interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'RDMO Sandbox', 'Back to project', 'Management', 'Admin', 'Language', and 'Hannes Fuchs'. Below this, a breadcrumb trail reads 'My Projects / MOSES DEMO NFDI4Earth 2024-12-13 / 2) Sensors and Instruments and their derived quantities'. The main heading is '2) Sensors and instruments used during the campaign'. A sub-heading reads 'Sensor information will be filled automatically in case the device is listed in a sensor management system (e.g. SMS, O2A REGISTRY, Geophysical Instrument Pool Potsdam) or has to be filled manually. If your sensor is listed in O2A REGISTRY, SMS or GIPP, then please enter a name, PID, or instrument type in the first field and select your device from the list. The form will be automatically filled and you just need to check. Otherwise please enter all required sensor details in the fields below.' A progress bar shows '77 of 94'. A search box contains the text 'cycle'. Below the search box, a list of search results is displayed, including entries from O2A REGISTRY, L1C, L6A, and AMMOD. A red box highlights the search input field.

My Projects / MOSES DEMO NFDI4Earth 2024-12-13 / 2) Sensors and Instruments and their derived quantities

2) Sensors and instruments used during the campaign

Sensor information will be filled automatically in case the device is listed in a sensor management system (e.g. SMS, O2A REGISTRY, Geophysical Instrument Pool Potsdam) or has to be filled manually. If your sensor is listed in O2A REGISTRY, SMS or GIPP, then please enter a name, PID, or instrument type in the first field and select your device from the list. The form will be automatically filled and you just need to check. Otherwise please enter all required sensor details in the fields below.

Campaign related information starts with questions 2.10)

Please fill in the form for each tab. The same tabs may be used later on other pages. You can add a new tab using the green button. Once created, you can edit or delete tabs using the buttons in the top right corner.

o2a-test gfz-test ufz-test sensor-example **+ Sensors and instruments used during the campaign**

2.1) Instrument identification for API search:

If your sensor is listed in any of the above listed databases, please enter here the name, type, manufacturer, serial number or PID... for the search. Then you should be able to select your device from the list and the following fields will be automatically filled.

Nevertheless, please check the entries below for correctness in case of automatic entries.

cycle

- O2A REGISTRY: thermistor package heat 208 (id: busy-2019-9/package_heat_208_klorid)
- O2A REGISTRY: Micromac 1000 A (s/n: 9999a, id: station.helmuwobs_fb_awi_730201.umac1000-a_9999a)
- O2A REGISTRY: L1C (id: station.neumayer_ii.igns-rr.igns_refracto11c)
- O2A REGISTRY: L6A (id: station.neumayer_ii.igns-rr.igns_refracto16a)
- O2A REGISTRY: Ammod Weather Station Compact WSC11 06223669 (s/n: 06223669, id: station.ammod_bs_003-weather_wsc11_06223669)
- O2A REGISTRY: LabSTAF - Single Turnover Active Fluorometer (id: fluorometer:labstaf_geomar)
- O2A REGISTRY: L2C (id: station.neumayer_ii.igns-rr.igns_refracto12c)
- O2A REGISTRY: Micromac 1000 B (s/n: 9999a, id: station.helmuwobs_fb_awi_730201.umac1000-b_9999a)
- O2A REGISTRY: thermistor package temp 208 (id: busy-2019-9/package_temp_208_klorid)
- O2A REGISTRY: Global Change Observation Mission - Water SHIZUKU (id: satellite:gcomw1)
- UFZ Sensors: Biometra T-Professional Gradient PCR Cycler (s/n: 3004250)
- UFZ Sensors: Biometra T-Professional Gradient PCR Cycler (s/n: 3004249)
- UFZ Sensors: Hamilton Star liquid handling system for molecular biology methods (s/n: 7907)

You might check out [here](#) for European trade marks or [here](#) for US trademarks.

Enter a search term and in the background multiple instrument/sensor registries are queried.

Currently the registries: O2A, GFZ/KIT/UFZ Sensor Management System and GIPP

Demo: Suggestions

RDMO Sandbox Back to project Management Admin Language Hannes Fuchs

My Projects / MOSES DEMO NFDI4Earth 2024-12-13 / 2) Sensors and Instruments and their derived quantities

2) Sensors and instruments used during the campaign

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o2a-test gtz-test ufz-test sensor-example **+ Sensors and instruments used during the campaign** 77 of 94

Back Proceed

2.1) Instrument identification for API search:

If your sensor is listed in any of the above listed databases, please enter here the name, type, manufacturer, serial number or PID... for the search. Then you should be able to select your device from the list and the following fields will be automatically filled.

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cycle

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- UFZ Sensors: Hamilton Star liquid handling system for molecular biology methods (s/n: 7907)

You might check out here for European trade marks or here for US trademarks.

Based on the search term a list of matched instruments/sensors to choose is displayed

Demo: Select an instrument/sensor

Select the desired instrument/sensor to fill out the other questions automatically

RDMO Sandbox Back to project Management Admin Language Hannes Fuchs

My Projects / MOSES DEMO NFDI4Earth 2024-12-13 / 2) Sensors and Instruments and their derived quantities

2) Sensors and instruments used during the campaign

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o2a-test gtz-test ufz-test sensor-example **+ Sensors and instruments used during the campaign** 77 of 94

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- O2A REGISTRY: L1C (id: station:neumayer_ii:gnss-r:gnss_refracto11c)
- O2A REGISTRY: L6A (id: station:neumayer_ii:gnss-r:gnss_refracto16a)
- O2A REGISTRY: Ammod Weather Station Compact WSC11 06223669 (s/n: 06223669, id: station:ammod_bs_003:weather_wsc11_06223669)
- O2A REGISTRY: LabSTAF - Single Turnover Active Fluorometer (id: fluorometer:labstaf_geomar)
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- O2A REGISTRY: thermistor package temp 208 (id: busy-2019-9:package_temp_208_klor3)
- O2A REGISTRY: Global Change Observation Masterplan (id: gcom-m:globalchangeobservationmasterplan)
- UFZ Sensors: Biometra T-Professional Gradient PCR Cycler (s/n: 3004250)**
- UFZ Sensors: Biometra T-Professional Gradient PCR Cycler (s/n: 0684649)
- UFZ Sensors: Hamilton Star liquid handling system for molecular biology methods (s/n: 7907)

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Demo: Automatically filled out questions

RDMO Sandbox Back to project Management Admin Language Hannes Fuchs

UFZ Sensors: Biometra T-Professional Gradient PCR Cycler (s/n: 3004250)

2.2) Name of instrument (from API search or manual entry):
The field will be filled automatically according to the entry in the respective sensor management system or has to be filled manually.
Biometra T-Professional Gradient PCR Cycler

2.3) Type of instrument (from API search or manual entry):
Short description for the instrument type. Examples: gas analyzer, infrared spectrometer, soil moisture probe, thermometer, lysimeter, anemometer, Lidar, water quality sensor, ...
Will be filled automatically in case the sensor is properly registered in a sensor management system. Otherwise try to use other controlled vocabularies such as [Glossary of Meteorology](#).
PCR

2.4) Instrument Manufacturer (from API search or manual entry):
Please provide the Manufacturer of the instrument.
Will be filled automatically in case the sensor is properly registered in a sensor management system.
You might check out [here](#) for European trade marks or [here](#) for US trademarks.
Biometra

2.5) Instrument Model (from API search or manual entry):
Please provide the instrument model.
Will be filled automatically in case the sensor is properly registered in a sensor management system.
T-Professional

2.6) Instrument Serial Number (from API search or manual entry):
Please try to provide a serial number or any given identifier (Antagenserummer) for the instrument! This is important to distinguish your sensor from other ones of the same type.
Will be filled automatically in case the sensor is properly registered in a sensor management system.
3004250

2.7) Unique Instrument Identification (from API search or manual entry):
Please enter PID (syntax: namespace/local name) if sensor is registered in B2INST, SMS, REGISTRY or other system providing a persistent unique sensor identifier (e.g handle, DOI).
Will be filled automatically in case the sensor is properly registered in a sensor management system.
21.11154/SMS-35121761-486d-4fc1-b559-c2768e4b869a

Questions are answered, based on the selected instrument/sensor

Data Management Plans at DKRZ

NFDI4Earth x DMP4NFDI Basic Service Workshop

Ivonne Anders

DKRZ - German Climate Computing Center

Some facts about the DKRZ

organizational structure and topics

- Non-profit GmbH since 1987
- Shareholder:
 - Max-Planck-Society (55%)
 - Free und Hanseatic City Hamburg (University Hamburg) (27%)
 - Alfred-Wegener-Institute (9%)
 - hereon (9%)
- Employees: ca. 120

Future Climate Simulations

... tell us something about possible future climate changes

Some facts about the DKRZ

organizational structure and topics

- central national service facility for climate and earth system research
- high-performance computers, data storage and services form the central research infrastructure
- support for the simulation-based climate science in Germany
- technical support for model calculations
- customized services
- develops relevant user software, advises and supports its users in IT matters
- participation in national and international projects and collaborations with the aim of further improving the infrastructure for climate modeling.

Does the DKRZ has a DMP service for all users?

project's brain

... yes and no ...

Does the DKRZ has a DMP service for all users?

Yes and **No**

- ✓ We do have a RDMO instance that every DKRZ user can log into, but **this DMP service is not offered for individual use.**

Why?: The reason is that there is **no need** for this, as the users of the shareholders have access to tools for DMPs and support in research data management via their institutions. All other users come to us for computing resources or to publish data

Does the DKRZ has a DMP service for all users?

Yes and No

- ✓ In **case DKRZ is responsible for the data management** in large projects, we create the DMP-templates and DMPs in RDMO and provide the access to the projects partners.
- ✓ When **users submit a request for computing time**, information on methods and storage space is also requested for the processing time and in the archive. A DMP must also be submitted for particularly large requests. We provide a template and give support in case of queries.

Does the DKRZ has a DMP service for all users?

Yes.

EXZELLENZCLUSTER

CLIMATE, CLIMATIC CHANGE,
AND SOCIETY (CLICCS)

3 main subject areas with a total of 14 projects focused on various research questions.

Challenges:

- only one DMP-template (DMP questionnaire) that covers the most diverse requirements, but also different types of results from the very different research areas (social sciences, law, climate sciences)
- transfer of the template to two different RDMO instances (DKRZ and ZFDM)

Does the DKRZ has a DMP service for all users?

Yes

- examples

large consortium projects (Horizon 2020 and BMBF FONA) with a number of work packages

Challenges:

- only one DMP for the whole project that includes the individual work packages
- access to the DMP for external partners

Data Management Plans at DKRZ

NFDI4Earth x DMP4NFDI Basic Service Workshop

Ivonne Anders

DKRZ - German Climate Computing Center

Summary:

great support from RDMO team!

- DMP service RDMO
- DMP-template creation
- DMPs for large projects
- DMPs connected to the usage of our resources.

Thank you!

Universität Hamburg
DER FORSCHUNG | DER LEHRE | DER BILDUNG

CENTER
FOR SUSTAINABLE
RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

DMP with RDMO @ UHH

13.12.2024 **Dr Stefan Thiemann**

Center for Sustainable Research Data Management at UHH

- Central „Operational unit“ (§93 HmbHG), assignment to VP Research
- Founded 2017, 8 FTE
- Cooperation with Data Centers, NFDI, Academy of Sciences and Humanities Hamburg
- **Our services at a glance**
 - Consulting, training and information
 - Research Data Repository (UHH-RDR)
 - Research Information System (UHH-RIS)
 - Providing of Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
 - Tool and consulting for Data Management Plans (DMP)
 - Curation of (web-)applications / Heurist database toolbox
 - Fundus Scientific Collections Portal
 - Chatbot for the UHH (UHHGPT)
 - Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELabFTW coming soon)
 - Open Access and Open Science

Photo: Pauli-Pirat

DMP with RDMO @ UHH

- On-site RDMO installation
<https://dmp.fdm.uni-hamburg.de/>
- Login with UHH identifier (Shibboleth)
- Small modifications (corporate design)
- RDMO is a stable application
- Sometimes issues with updates

LOGIN

ZENTRUM
FÜR NACHHALTIGES
FORSCHUNGSDATENMANAGEMENT

Welcome to RDMO

The aim of the RDMO project is to deliver a web application to assist structured planning, implementation and administration of the data in a scientific project. Additionally, the gathered information can be cast into textual forms suitable for funding agencies requirements or for reports.

This is a prototype of the software, for demonstration purposes.

For more information about the project visit rdmorganiser.github.io.

Login

Photo: UHH

DMP with RDMO @ UHH

• RDMO templates

- Bielefeld
- Cost overview
- DMPonline
- DMPTool
- Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP
- **CLICCS (Cluster of Excellence)**

Views

Views are created using the answers given in the project and can then be exported in various formats. Initially, all views are empty. Please answer some questions by visiting **Answer Questions** (at the top of the sidebar).

View	Description	
CLICCS (Initial phase) RDMO view version 1.0	View (export template) for CLICCS (initial phase), funded by DFG.	
Bielefeld	DMP template from the University of Bielefeld.	
Cost overview [de]	Overview of the personnel and non-personnel costs [de]	
Cost overview [en]	Overview of the personnel and non-personnel costs [en]	
DMPonline template	Template from DMPonline, online https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk	
DMPTool template	Template from DMPTool, based on "NSF-GEN: Generic", online: https://dmptool.org	
Horizon 2020 FAIR Data Management Plan template	Template for Horizon 2020, from "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020", online: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf	

Photo: UHH

DMP with RDMO @ UHH

- CLICCS (Cluster of Excellence) – reduced list of questions
- DMP mandatory for CLICCS sub-projects
 - „Data manager“ in sub-projects
 - CLICCS data management guidelines
 - review of the DMP
 - more than 20 DMP

1. Data classification and care

1.1. Type, purpose, size

1. What kind of data was or will be generated by the CLICCS sub-project?
2. What is the purpose of the data and its relation to the objectives of the project?
3. What is the (expected) size of the generated data?

1.2. Disciplines

4. Which disciplines (DFG subject areas) does the data belong to?

Dataset Collection test data:

1.3. Provenance

5. What is the processing history of the generated data?
6. If re-used, was the data created within CLICCS?

Dataset collection test data:

7. If some data has been re-used, under which addresses, identifiers, or URLs can the data be found?

Dataset collection test data:

8. To whom might your generated data be useful ('data utility'), within the CLICCS sub-project, for other CLICCS sub-projects, or outside CLICCS?

Dataset collection test data:

1.4. Data Management

Photo: UHH

DMP with RDMO @ UHH

- **Little use of the service across the university**
 - no (real) commitment from funders
 - perceived as too complex
 - user guidance and interface should be improved
 - too many questions in standard templates
 - data could not be reused (no value)
- ➔ We are working on a link to our data repository.**

Thank you very much! Questions?

Contact

Center for Sustainable Research Data Management

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Summary of the workshop

- We discussed with the group of about 30 workshop participants, consisting of DMP4NFDI representatives, NFDI4Earth and related DMP service providers, other service providers, representatives of the NFDI4Earth helpdesk, data stewards from different institutes, and DMP interested, the developed approaches, solutions, and experiences.
- The next slides summarize the main aspects addressed in the group discussion.

What are DMP use cases in the NFDI4Earth community?

- The NFDI4Earth community includes DMP service providers, DMP service users, such as data stewards, as well as researchers.
- DMP use cases cover a wide range:
- Organising data management across diverse groups in large joint research projects, such as the excellence cluster [CLICCS](#),
- Organising data management across diverse services / infrastructures in large joint research projects, e.g., [MOSES](#)
- Acquisition of HPC resources and documentation of the data management with costly services

What are DMP offers in the NFDI4Earth community?

- NFDI4Earth partners offer diverse (institutional) solutions, e.g.,
 - DKRZ's RDMO (<https://rdmo.cloud.dkrz.de/>)
 - Uni Hamburg's RDMO (<https://www.fdm.uni-hamburg.de/service/rdmo.html>),
 - IÖR's ROMPi approach (<https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2024-034>),
 - FU Berlin's DMP consulting including information on openly available services (see [here](#))
 - TU Dresden Service Center Research Data's individual DMP solution (see [here](#))
 - GEOMAR's individual DMP templates or guidelines, e.g., the [CDRmare DMP Template](#) or [the central research data guidelines](#)
- The community also offers cross-domain services and information, e.g.,
 - SaxFDM (<https://saxfdm.de/fokusprojekte/>), [Forschungsdaten.org](https://www.forschungsdaten.org)

What does DMP4NFDI & RDMO offer?

- Central RDMO instance (hosted at TU Darmstadt) and (test) clients for the consortia
- Support to maintain templates and questions
- Support cross-consortia DMP management
- DMP4NFDI currently works on a template framework with a common core for all consortia (see also related NFDI working groups)
- RDMO is available as an open-source project for self-hosting:
<https://github.com/rdmorganiser>
- RDMO provides a couple of plugins that could also be of relevance for NFDI4Earth, e.g., to integrate/link other services like Zenodo, Wikidata, RADAR, etc. :
<https://github.com/rdmorganiser?q=plugins&type=all&language=&sort=>
- RDMO questions are maintained in GitHub: <https://github.com/rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/tree/master-rdmo2.x/rdmorganiser/Questions>

What are potential usage scenarios in NFDI4Earth? (1/2)

- Scenario 1
 - NFDI4Earth will use the DMP4NFDI-provided test client: <https://rdmo-test.nfdi4earth.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/projects/> that can be changed to a central productive client for the NFDI4Earth community.
 - The client will use specific plugins to integrate community-developed and NFDI4Earth-developed services in close collaboration with DMP4NFDI.
 - The client can reuse existing (cross-consortia) templates
 - The NFDI4Earth Helpdesk will act as 1st Level Support for the central client, in particular, for ESS-specific requests, DMP4NFDI will act as 2nd (support template creation) / 3rd level support (support technical administration / plugin development).

What are potential usage scenarios in NFDI4Earth? (2/2)

- Scenario 2
 - NFDI4Earth will not provide/support a central DMP service as existing solutions already meet the users' needs.
 - The NFDI4Earth Helpdesk will support partners to find/develop proper solutions
- Scenario 3
 - An NFDI4Earth partner opens an existing DMP service for usage in the NFDI4Earth community.
 - Existing support structures will be linked to the NFDI4Earth Helpdesk

For all scenarios: NFDI4Earth will coordinate/moderate input for cross-consortial activities in the NFDI section's working group

Next steps

- Document and share the workshop outcomes with the ESS community
- Stimulate interactions in related NFDI section working groups
- Initiate follow-up discussions with DMP4NFDI and active use case partners
- Bring together DMP4NFDI team and NFDI4Earth User Support Network team
- Allow the NFDI4Earth community to test the DMP4NFDI-provided NFDI4Earth client and collect feedback
- Learn more about community needs for a „Geo“ basic DMP template and who can support the development
- Prepare NFDI basic service decision process with NFDI4Earth steering group
- ...

Contact

- DMP4NFDI: dmp4nfdi@lists.nfdi.de
- NFDI4Earth: helpdesk@nfdi4earth.de